

Evaluating an LLM-Based Phenotype Extractor from Medical Reports Using Combinatorial Testing

This is the replication package for the paper "Evaluating an LLM-Based Phenotype Extractor from Medical Reports Using Combinatorial Testing".

The LLM-based phenotype extractor is available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17912782>, including all configuration files, scripts, and instructions on how to set up and use the extractor.

Requirements for this Replication Package

Before running the scripts, install the following dependencies:

For the Majority of programs operating with csv:

```
pip install pandas
```

For translation:

```
pip install deep_translator
```

For scripts operating on the HPO ontology:

```
pip install pronto
```

The HPO ontology, contained into the file `hp.obo`, is also required, and must be stored under the `utils` directory.

You can download it from the following link: <https://hpo.jax.org/data/ontology>

Usage

Folder Structure

- The folder contains Python scripts that process and analyze data.
- The CSV files are located in the `output` folder. The following are the most important ones:
 - `merged_dataset.csv`: the merged dataset containing medical reports and their associated phenotypes.
 - `merged_dataset_with_parents.csv`: the merged dataset containing medical reports and their associated phenotypes, including parent codes.
 - `2wise_test_suite.csv`: the combinatorial test suite generated from the dataset.
- The `utils` folder contains utility python scripts and utility files.

- The `prompts` folder contains the prompts used for the LLM-based phenotype extractor during testing.
- The `results` folder contains the results of the experiments
 - `CombinatorialPromptTesting.xlsx` reports the summary data of the experiments.
 - `summary_*.csv` files contain the output of each test execution.
 - `results_analysis.py` contains the script used to analyze the results and to extract summary values.
 - `random/` contains the results of the random testing process.
- The `test_scripts` folder contains the scripts used to run the LLM-based phenotype extractor on the generated test cases.

Dataset Preparation

This replication package already contains the resulting datasets (`merged_dataset.csv` and `merged_dataset_with_parents.csv`). Thus, users who don't need to translate or merge datasets can skip this section.

- `save_and_prepare_database.py`: It saves the dataset needed for further operations. Then, it translates a specific dataset (translates 10 rows to English per cycle), and merges the two datasets into a single file. It also customizes the dataset by adding different names for patients, physicians, and hospitals. The script uses some of the functionalities offered by `utils/ontology_depth.py`.

After running this program, you will have a dataset named `merged_dataset.csv` and one named `merged_dataset_with_parents.csv` containing also parent codes.

The functionalities of `save_and_prepare_database.py` exploits the file `utils/names.py` which contains the names of patients, physicians, and hospitals.

IPM Creation

- `generate_ipm.py`: It generates the IPM, for a given depth and number of parameters. The IPM is saved in a file named `hpo.ctw`, in CTWedge format, and `hpo.acts` in the format compatible with CAgen. To perform the translation, the script uses the functionalities offered by `utils/ctwedge_to_acts_translator.py`.

Combinatorial sampling

- `combinatorial_sampling.py`: It generates the file `2wise_test_suite.csv` which contains the real test cases to be executed against the LLM.

Test execution

After the dataset (`2wise_test_suite.csv`) is ready and the LLM-based phenotype extractor is set up (see <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17912782>) and stored in the `test_scripts` folder, you can run the tests using the scripts in the `test_scripts` folder.

In particular, the **combinatorial prompt testing** process is executed through the file `test_scripts/PhenotypeExtractorTesting.py`, while the exhaustive prompt testing is executed through the file `test_scripts/PhenotypeExtractorTestingExhaustive.py`.

Analysis scripts

- **utis/dataset_analysis.py**: It checks how many of the phenotypes in HPO are not covered by the dataset. It considers the dataset stored in the `output/merged_dataset_with_parents.csv` file, and the combinatorial test suite in `output/2wise_test_suite.csv`.
- **utis/random_dataset_analysis.py**: It checks how many of the phenotypes in the original dataset are covered by random tests. It considers the dataset stored in the `results/random` folder, and the dataset stored in the `output/merged_dataset_with_parents.csv` file.